

ISic0468

A dedication to the Caesars by L. Caelius Quadratus

Language

Latin

Type

dedication

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Phintias

Place of origin (modern)

Licata

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Licata, not located

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Caesarib(us)
2. sacrum
3. L(ucius) Caelius M(arci) f(ilius)
4. Quadratus
5. d(e) s(ua) p(ecunia)

Apparatus

Text of CIL

Translation (en)

Sacred to the Caesars. Lucius Caelius Quadratus, son of Marcus (dedicated this) at his own expense

Commentary

The inscription appears to be lost, recorded first in Fazello 1558

Digital identifiers:

TM 491697

EDCS 21900532

Bibliography

Fazello, Tommaso 1558. F. Thomæ Fazelli... de rebus Siculis decades duæ. Panormi. At Dec. 1, book 5, p.23

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7191 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883>)

Manganaro, G. 1988. La Sicilia da Sesto Pompeo a Diocleziano. *ANRW*. 2.11.1: 3-89. At 47

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